

Calibrating white dwarf asteroseismology

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Abstract

The main goal of looking for variability in stars is the unique opportunity to study their internal structure. Once we have extracted independent modes, it appears to be a simple matter of comparing the observed period spectrum with those from theoretical model grids.

However, we must account not only for observational uncertainties in period determination, but most importantly for the limitations of the model grids, coming from the uncertainties in the constitutive physics, and the fitting techniques.

In this paper, we will discuss results of numerical experiments, using different independently calculated model grids (WDEC and LPCODE-PUL) and fitting techniques to fit synthetic stars. The advantage of using synthetic stars is that we know the details of their interior structure so we can assess how well our models and fitting techniques are able to recover the interior structure, as well as the stellar parameters.

1 Introduction

Stellar variability is observed in nearly all phases of stellar evolution, regardless of stellar mass. Through asteroseismological studies, we have the unique opportunity to use the observed pulsation modes to constrain the internal structure of the stars and, in turn, stellar evolution.

The vast majority of stars will end up their evolution as white dwarfs. For single stars, it is estimated that approximately 95 to 98% will become white dwarfs (Winget & Kepler, 2008). In this evolutionary stage, stars are basically cooling. As white dwarfs cool down, they cross three distinct instability strips, depending on their temperature and on the presence or not of the element that drives pulsations.

The coldest white dwarf instability strip is observed in a 2,000 K–width range, at temperatures close to 12,000 K, depending on the mass; massive white dwarfs start to pulsate at hotter temperatures, while low mass stars, at lower temperatures. Pulsations at these temperatures are observed only for hydrogen-dominated atmosphere (DAs) white dwarfs. Hydrogen atmospheres are detected in roughly 85% of all white dwarfs (Kepler *et al.*, 2016). We focus our efforts in this instability strip: DAVs or ZZ Cetus.

Qualitatively, the internal structure of a DA white dwarf is rather simple: a compact degenerated core consistent of a mixture of carbon and oxygen, surrounded by a thin envelope of helium and hydrogen. At the temperatures close to the instability strip, white dwarfs should have gone through gravitational settling, therefore, helium and hydrogen should be already separated. In order to determine the abundances of the layers, as well as mass and temperature, we must have access to many independent measurements, i.e. independent pulsation modes.

One would suppose that the internal structure of white dwarfs are easy to model. However, their intrinsically simple structure imposes additional challenges: white dwarfs are observed to pulsate with a small number of independent modes, which in turn limits the number of physical quantities that can be derived (Castanheira & Kepler, 2009). When we compare the few observed modes to model grids to derive multiple physical quantities, we obtain many families of solutions.

An even greater problem arises upon the calculation of models using different assumptions for a given model grid. Despite our qualitatively understanding of the internal structure of white dwarfs, when we compute detailed stellar models, we make many approximations in the physics, namely treatment of convection, diffusion recipes, mass loss processes, among others. Each model grid is calculated differently, therefore, the output structures are expected to be different. Regardless what white dwarf model we use and which approximations we make, we can compute the gravity modes period spectrum for each model, and compare the observed modes with the calculated periods.

Instead of comparing the profiles of the internal structures calculated in the models, we decided to compare directly the pulsation modes from one model grid to another. Our main goal is to determine how the differences in the computed internal structures will affect the pulsation modes. We want to estimate the external uncertainties for each physical quantity due to the choice of model grid.

2 Model Grids

We have calculated hundreds of thousands of models using WDEC (White Dwarf Evolutionary Code), described in Lamb & van Horn (1975) and Wood (1990). The starting point is a hot polytrope. The core evolution calculations are self-consistent but the envelope is treated separately. Both core and envelope are stitched and smoothed together. We have computed models with masses between 0.5 and 1.1 M_{\odot} , in steps of 0.005 M_{\odot} , temperatures between 10,600 and 12,600 K, with steps of 50 K, hydrogen mass layer between $\log M_{\text{H}} = -4$ and -9.5 , with steps of 0.5 dex, and helium mass layer between $\log M_{\text{He}} = -2$ and -4 , with steps of 0.5 dex. We have also used a core composition with a fixed ratio mixture of carbon and oxygen 50:50 (Castanheira & Kepler, 2008).

Our choices in parameter space for temperature and mass are based on the observed ZZ Cetus. The atmospheric parameters effective temperature and surface gravity are derived by fitting the spectra or photometry to model grids. As for the thickness of the hydrogen and helium layers, we chose the ranges based on theoretical calculations. Even in the white

dwarf cooling sequence, if the stars end up with too much hydrogen or helium, after the ejection of the outer layers during the thermal pulses, the star should experience explosive burning of these elements, leading to the so-called born again scenario. Our upper limits for hydrogen and helium are set to prevent a final burn (Hine, 1988). The lower limit for hydrogen layer thickness is based on spectroscopy: if the stars are left with less hydrogen than that, the stars would not be seen as DAs, but as DBs (helium-dominated atmospheres). The lower limit for the helium layer is coming directly from theoretical calculations on the previous evolutionary phases.

With the exception of temperature and mass which are mainly coming from observations, it is important to note that these limits are largely dependent on theoretical calculations and that different assumptions might lead to slightly different values.

We compared our WDEC fine model grid with synthetic stars, calculated with the LPCODE-PUL. The starting point for this model grid is a main sequence star with mass between 1 and 5 M_{\odot} , assuming solar-like metallicity. In these calculations, the internal structure of the white dwarfs, i.e. thicknesses of hydrogen and helium, core composition and mass, is determined by their evolution (Althaus *et al.*, 2010). The calculations of the models are stopped at specific temperatures. The only way to expand this model grid is to “remove” portions of the hydrogen layer.

3 Comparison between two model grids

In order to compare both model grids, we have created what we call “synthetic stars”. We used the physical parameters calculated by the LPCODE-PUL to be compared to the WDEC model grid.

Our major challenge is to decide which pulsation modes we will use to make this comparison. We chose a sample of 8 classical ZZ Ceti (Fontaine & Brassard, 2008). For each object, we use the list of theoretical periods corresponding to the best fit model obtained by Romero *et al.* (2012). We consider the pulsation amplitude as that observed by the corresponding period.

The comparison between the modes were calculated as the sum of the differences, following the expression:

$$S^2 = \frac{\sum_i^n (P_{\text{obs}} - P_{\text{model}})^2}{\sum_i^n n} \quad (1)$$

where P_{obs} are the periods selected in the LPCODE-PUL star, P_{model} are the periods in the WDEC models, and n is the number of periods in the fit.

In the Table 1, we list the results of our fits.

3.1 Uncertainties

Besides the best model fit, in Table 1 we also listed the uncertainties in each fit. Our internal uncertainties were calculated as:

$$\sigma^2 = \frac{d^2}{S - S_0} \quad (2)$$

where d is the difference between a physical quantity, S_0 is the sum of differences for the best model, and S is the sum of differences for a model when we vary a given physical quantity by the amount d . We followed the formulation of Zhang *et al.* (1986).

When discussing the uncertainties, we have to discuss which uncertainty we are referring to. As mentioned above,

WDEC model grid has four dimensions: effective temperature (T_{eff}), stellar mass (M), mass of the hydrogen layer (M_{H}), and mass of the helium layer (M_{He}). In general terms, we have to differentiate between internal and external uncertainties of the measurement. The internal uncertainty is calculated when we vary the physical quantities one at a time, around the best model. For the external uncertainty, we will consider the differences between two consecutive minima. We are listing here the internal uncertainties only, because, in most cases, we can distinguish between these solutions with additional measurements, for instance, if we would have spectroscopic measurements (Tremblay *et al.*, 2013).

3.2 Rotation

The calculated model grids do not account for rotation, therefore we are calculating only $m = 0$ modes. Some stars could have been observed in an unfavorable angle and we might be observing $m = \pm 1$ modes.

Following the formulation by Kepler *et al.* (1983), the velocity of the rotation at the equator is given by:

$$v_r = 2\pi R \Delta f (1 - C_{k\ell}^I)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where

$$C_{k\ell}^I = [\ell(\ell + 1)]^{-1} \quad (4)$$

For $\ell = 1$, the asymptotic value is $C_{k\ell}^I = 0.5$. Considering the rotation periods of white dwarfs to be of the order of 1 day, we estimate that $\Delta f \sim 5 \mu\text{Hz}$. We propagate that uncertainty in frequency to the observed periods and fitted them to the model grids. Even though we used the “wrong” m value, due to rotation, when fitting the models we would recover the exact same models (Metcalfe, 2003).

Observationally, to measure the rotation rate of stars, it is necessary to have a long baseline of observations. Hermes *et al.* (2017) measured the rotation rates for 27 white dwarfs observed by *Kepler/K2*. Despite some extreme cases, our estimates are consistent with their measurements.

3.3 Degree ℓ of the pulsation modes

Due to geometric cancellation, photometrically, it is much more likely to observe $\ell = 1$ rather than 2 (Robinson *et al.*, 1982). Robinson *et al.* (1995) proposed to use the changes in amplitude variation of the modes as a function of wavelength. Previous studies by Kepler *et al.* (2000) used ultraviolet time-series of spectroscopy to determine the ℓ degree for the observed modes of four white dwarfs. We understand that it is not a statistically significant sample, but these are the best determinations to date of this quantity. All observed modes for these stars are more likely to be $\ell = 1$ than 2 and even more likely than any other higher value.

We do not have any additional information of the ℓ degree modes of the stars. Therefore, we will use the geometric cancellation and the determinations of these four stars to justify why we constrained our fitting to $\ell = 1$ modes. For some stars, we have observed modes that are too close in period, which cannot have the same $\ell = 1$ value. In these cases, we have allowed our fits to be $\ell = 1$ and 2.

Adding the ℓ degree in the fits adds an extra degree of freedom. Each extra parameter that is added translates into additional families of solutions, especially if the stars have intrinsically a small number of independent measurements.

Table 1: Asteroseismologic fits to WDEC model grid of “synthetic stars” calculated using the LPCODE.

SYNTHETIC STAR	Periods (ℓ)	LPCODE	WDEC
		T_{eff} (K), M (M_{\odot}), M_{H} (M_{\star}), M_{He} (M_{\star})	T_{eff} (K), M (M_{\odot}), M_{H} (M_{\star}), M_{He} (M_{\star})
G117-B15A	215.215 s (1) 273.437 s (1) 301.854 s (1)	11985, 0.593, $10^{-5.9}$, $10^{-1.62}$	11900 ± 100 , 0.62 ± 0.03 , $10^{-7 \pm 0.5}$, $10^{-2 \pm 0.5}$
HS0507+0434B	356.737 s (1) 446.424 s (1) 556.767 s (1) 742.920 s (1)	12257, 0.660, $10^{-4.25}$, $10^{-1.92}$	12100 ± 200 , 0.62 ± 0.04 , $10^{-6 \pm 0.5}$, $10^{-3 \pm 0.5}$
G191-16	509.983 s (1) 598.812 s (1) 712.027 s (1) 893.495 s (1)	11741, 0.632, $10^{-4.86}$, $10^{-1.75}$	11700 ± 50 , 0.85 ± 0.22 , $10^{-9.5 \pm 0.5}$, $10^{-3 \pm 0.5}$
GD244	195.973 s (2) 257.215 s (1) 296.820 s (2) 306.283 s (1) 906.176 s (1)	12422, 0.593, $10^{-3.93}$, $10^{-1.62}$	12200 ± 200 , 0.82 ± 0.01 , $10^{-8.5 \pm 0.5}$, $10^{-2.5 \pm 0.5}$
G226-29	109.246 s (1)	12270, 0.77, $10^{-4.69}$, $10^{-1.225}$	11600 ± 5000 , 0.72 ± 0.47 , $10^{-4 \pm 3.3}$, $10^{-2 \pm 3.3}$
GD66	198.104 s (2) 256.137 s (2) 271.804 s (1) 300.102 s (1)	12068, 0.593, $10^{-6.33}$, $10^{-1.62}$	11600 ± 1300 , 0.88 ± 0.09 , $10^{-7 \pm 2.2}$, $10^{-3 \pm 0.73}$
G185-32	215.739 s (1) 269.253 s (2) 298.724 s (2) 367.694 s (1) 652.677 s (1)	11721, 0.66, $10^{-6.35}$, $10^{-1.91}$	11900 ± 260 , 0.605 ± 0.14 , $10^{-9 \pm 2.2}$, $10^{-2 \pm 0.43}$
R548	187.597 s (1) 213.401 s (1) 242.263 s (1) 311.361 s (2) 336.504 s (2)	11627, 0.609, $10^{-5.96}$, $10^{-1.61}$	11900 ± 490 , 0.62 ± 0.03 , $10^{-5 \pm 5}$, $10^{-3 \pm 0.8}$

Table 2: Average external uncertainties due to the model grids LPCODE vs. WDEC

$$\begin{aligned}
 \sigma_{T_{\text{eff}}} &= 130 \text{ K} \\
 \sigma_M &= 0.13 M_{\odot} \\
 \sigma_{M_{\text{H}}} &= 3 \text{ dex} \\
 \sigma_{M_{\text{He}}} &= 0.9 \text{ dex}
 \end{aligned}$$

4 Results and Discussions

After the choices of periods and the comparisons between the model grids, we have estimated additional uncertainties that should be factored into the asteroseismological fits: the choice of model grids. We list in Table 2, the average uncertainties calculated for each quantity that are associated to the models.

Our work is just a first attempt to quantify the additional uncertainties, due to differences in the model grids. The future step is to fit more synthetic stars, with various masses and temperatures, across the ZZ Ceti instability strip. It would be worth to investigate by how much changes in the number of periods in the fits would affect the uncertainty in

choice of different model grids.

In addition, we plan to expand our analysis to other model grids. We are in the process of calculating pulsation modes for the models computed using MESA (Paxton *et al.*, 2011). MESA is an open source suite of stellar evolution models. These stellar models are self-consistent, which means, for a given mass and metallicity, the white dwarf will have a well-defined structure. The only way to produce a different star would be to vary the input physics in the calculation of the models (e.g. diffusion recipe). However, that brings us back to the initial discussion on the intrinsically simple structure of white dwarfs: the limited number of observables. For the near future, we will not change the input physics of MESA and simply compute models to build our synthetic stars.

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